

INTERNATIONAL WOMEN, PEACE, AND SECURITY

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Abstract

Despite overwhelming evidence of rampant sexual violence in armed conflicts, it took the United Nations Security Council (UNSC) - the only body empowered to address issues of international peace and security, fifty-five years to pass its first resolution on women, peace and security (WPS). The article discusses the importance of the first WPS resolution 1325 and lists the subsequent resolutions on WPS that elaborates on the prevention, protection aspects of sexual violence in conflicts. It also explores the feminist critiques on the limitations of the WPS agenda, particularly how they fall short in acknowledging the root causes of sexual violence in conflicts that results in a violence continuum not limited to armed conflict. The article concludes that the valid critiques notwithstanding, WPS agenda of the UNSC remains important and relevant to address issues of violence against women in conflicts.

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Introduction

Post the end of the cold war, the nature of armed conflicts shifted from being primarily between two countries, to being internal conflicts within states. Civilian populations were both the target and the means of warfare in these internal conflicts. Several United Nations (UN) humanitarian interventions were launched in conflict-ridden and unstable countries. By the end of the 1990s, there was a change seen through the huge streams of refugees and internally displaced persons in conflicts throughout Africa and in the Balkans. These conflicts saw exponential growth in the use of sexualized violence as a tool of war and means of combat, primarily but not exclusively directed against women. (Tryggestad, 2009)

Women are impacted by conflicts in several different ways. The coercive nature of conflict itself raises personal and physical vulnerability. Women and girls experience random and targeted sexual and gender-based violence, are vulnerable to being trafficked into sexual slavery, forced labour, enforced prostitution, and other forms of violence. Conflict causes disruption of family and social lives. Overnight, communities are disrupted. Men join, are recruited or conscripted, into the state or rebel armed forces to engage in combat. Homes and whole villages are destroyed leaving women landless and homeless, forcing them into relief and refugee camps that are constructed overnight in cramped spaces. Women are left to fend for themselves and care for the young and old of the community with little knowledge and/or skills on how to go about doing it.

Women and families face food, livelihood, job, income insecurities, and are dependent on aid for their subsistence. Women who have been kept away from the labour market have no option but to enter the workforce and without any skills end up in low-paying jobs or exploitative labour conditions. There is a rise in maternal and infant mortality rates and a big impact on access to sexual and reproductive health services. The experience of conflict, the disruption of their lives, the vulnerability and experience of sexual and gender-based violence causes severe mental health problems for women, particularly trauma, depression, anxiety, and fear, severely impacting the quality of their lives. Women are forced to take an increased public or leadership role to gain access to services in refugee camps, go out to earn income for their households, organise care of the young and elderly in the camps, engage in cross-party peace initiatives, campaigns, and/or protests to end conflict, organise and work towards justice and reconciliation initiatives.

There are several UN bodies, committees and processes that address issues of women's rights and women's empowerment—Commission on Status of Women (CSW), Conventions on Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW), and Special Rapporteur on Violence Against

Women to name a few. (UN.org, n.d.) None of these, however, have the mandate to deal directly with issues of women in conflict as they fall in the category of international peace and security, a domain exclusively entrusted to the United Nations Security Council (UNSC).

The UNSC on Women, Peace and Security (WPS)

UNSC derives its mandate from the UN Charter in Articles 23–32 adopted in 1945 at the first meeting of member-states in San Francisco. These articles state the basics of its structure, its functions, the voting rights and participation of non-members. UNSC is a fifteen-member Council and has five permanent members—Russia, China, the US, the UK and France—with veto powers. 10 members are elected every two years. Each member has one vote and decisions are made by an affirmative vote of nine members, including concurring vote of the permanent five. A non-member party to a dispute under consideration by the Council, is invited to participate, without vote, in the discussion relating to the dispute. (UN.org, n.d.)

The primary responsibility of the UNSC is to maintain international peace and security. Towards that end, the UNSC regularly passes resolutions to note escalating situations of conflict in any part of the world, designating conflicts as threat to international peace and security, calling for ceasefire, imposing sanctions and/or embargoes, sending peacekeeping forces, and establishing committees/subcommittees, tribunals and other mechanisms to deal with ongoing conflict crises or post-conflict reconstruction.

There is a distinction between Council non-coercive resolutions adopted under Chapter VI and coercive resolutions adopted under Chapter VII of the UN Charter. Resolutions under Chapter VII are invoked when there is a reasonable belief that a breach of the peace has occurred or a threat to international peace and security is imminent. These resolutions are considered binding on member states. Chapter VI resolutions are of a non-coercive nature that is a normative persuasion with an intention to induce favourable short or long-term conduct of member-states on the thematic of the resolution at local or international spaces. (Tryggestad, 2009)

For the longest time, there has been practically no interest among the most powerful member states of the Council to discuss issues other than ongoing conflicts or immediate threats to international peace and security. (Tryggestad, 2009) The changing nature of conflict from interstate to intrastate or internal conflicts also led to a change, to some extent reluctant, in the attitudes of members of the Council toward thematic issues such as WPS.

UNSC Resolutions on WPS

Historically, there has been a strict division between soft and hard issue areas

within the UN. Women's issues have traditionally been relegated to the domains of soft policy, and thus were not something to which the Council was required to pay attention to. There had been, for a long time, a formal barrier between promotion of women's rights i.e., traditionally 'soft' socio-political issues and 'hard' security issues of international peace and security. The first resolution passed by the UNSC on women, peace and security, Resolution 1325, broke this barrier. Since then, WPS has appeared as a normative issue that is increasingly difficult for member states to neglect or ignore.

Resolution 1325, passed in October, 2000 is a ground-breaking resolution that addresses the issues of representation, inclusion of gender perspective, and protection of women in conflict environments. The resolution urges member states to increase the representation and active participation of women at all decision-making levels in national, regional, and international institutions and mechanisms for conflict prevention, conflict management, conflict resolution, and peacebuilding. The resolution encourages member-states to adopt a gender perspective in the planning and implementation of peace operations and peace negotiations—including gender-sensitive training of personnel, an expanded role for women as peacekeepers, and increased attention to local women's peace initiatives, needs, and interests in mission areas. The resolution also emphasises the need for increased attention to the protection and respect of women's rights, including protection against gender-based violence in situations of armed conflict and initiatives to put an end to impunity for such crimes. (Peacewomen, n.d.)

1325 is a non-coercive resolution and its language is therefore of a persuasive nature. It was one of the reasons for the unanimous Council vote in favour of the Resolution. 'The thematic issue of WPS was seen by the members of the Council at the time as having low priority and few, if any, serious implications for them in practice. A peace strategist working on conflicts, Sanam Anderlini remarks, in any case, that "in all likelihood, Council members were not fully aware of the way in which women's groups in civil society, governments, and the UN system would keep resolution 1325 alive."' (Tryggestad, 2009, p. 544)

Resolution 1325 was so successfully kept alive that it is followed by 10 other resolutions on different aspects of WPS that clarifies representation or gender perspective, enhances protection and adds other aspects of WPS that were missing. The success was, however, slow to come by with the next resolution after 1325 coming eight years later. Resolution 1820 of 2008 further strengthened the protection aspect of the WPS agenda, addressed sexual violence in conflict and post-conflict situations. It noted that sexual violence can constitute a war crime, a crime against humanity, or a constitutive act with respect to genocide. (Peacewomen, n.d.)

The Council's intent to strengthen protection against sexual violence was reinforced with resolution 1888 of 30 September 2009, which established the position of Special Representative on Sexual Violence in Conflict (the Special Representative) to report on the worldwide status of sexual violence in conflict. The resolution also includes specific provisions for protection of women and children from sexual violence in the mandates of peacekeeping operations. Resolution 1889 the same year notes obstacles for women's full participation in the peace processes. (Peacewomen, n.d.)

Further strengthening the mandate of the Special Representative, resolution 1960 of 2010 requested the Secretary General to add an annex to the annual report on conflict-related sexual violence listing conflict parties "that are credibly suspected of committing or being responsible for patterns of rape and other forms of sexual violence in situations of armed conflict on the Security Council agenda". In the resolution, the Council expressed its intention to use this annex "as a basis for more focused United Nations engagement with those parties", which could include targeted sanctions. Furthermore, the Council called upon the parties to armed conflict "to make and implement specific and time-bound commitments to combat sexual violence". (Peacewomen, n.d.)

Resolution 2100 of 2013 invited the Secretary General to "commission a global study on the implementation of 1325". Another resolution the same year 2106 emphasised how crucial prevention of sexual violence is to international peace and security. Resolution 2242 passed in 2015 incorporated recommendations from that study. In 2016, yet another important resolution no.2272 was passed in which the Council addressed sexual exploitation and abuse by UN peacekeepers. Among other measures in response to the problem, it endorsed a previous decision by the Secretary General to repatriate units in peace-keeping operations in cases "when there is credible evidence of widespread or systemic sexual exploitation and abuse by that unit." (Peacewomen, n.d.)

There were two resolutions passed in 2019. The first one—2467—focused on conflict-related sexual violence, "recognizing the need for a survivor-centered approach to preventing and responding to sexual violence in conflict and post-conflict situations". The second resolution—2493—reiterated the need for the full implementation of the women, peace and security agenda and expressed deep concern about the existence of persistent barriers to that end. (Peacewomen, n.d.)

Advocacy on WPS

As Anderlini indicates, the UNSC resolutions on WPS came about because of intense advocacy by women's groups in civil society, some member-states supported by other agencies of the UN. Advocacy at UNSC on WPS primarily

involves getting desired language in the above stated UNSC resolutions on various aspects of WPS and influencing the UNSC Presidential statements with key concerns on implementation of UNSC resolutions on WPS, clarification or elaboration on the UNSC resolutions and inclusion of presidential responses/acknowledgement of UN Secretary General (UNSG) reports on WPS. It also often includes blocking new resolutions to dilute or weaken the languages in existing resolution on WPS. A member-state in the position of President of the UNSC has the power to introduce a resolution whether or not it is needed. In 2021, Russia, as the President of UNSC, introduced a resolution on WPS with language that was regressive. The advocacy efforts of various civil society groups (CSGs) and member-states ensured that the resolution was defeated.

The main space for advocacy is the annual WPS open debate held in October on the occasion of the anniversary of the first UNSC Resolution 1325. The debate is organised by member states that often introduce new topics for debate and discussion. The agenda of the open debates are informed by the Secretary General's annual report on Women Peace and Security and other matters that nation state hosting the debate prioritises. The open debate is a forum where the Council hears statements from briefers, Security Council members, and other Member States. The 11 UNSC resolutions on WPS passed are often the outcome document of the annual open debate. The briefers usually include the UN Secretary General, the Executive Director of UN Women, representatives of other UN agencies, and a civil society representative selected by the NGO Working Group on Women, Peace and Security (NGOWG). The NGOWG is a large coalition of women's and civil society groups working on concerns of women in conflict from around the world including those from conflict regions.

Ahead of the UNSC meeting on peace and security issues, Canada hosts an informal group of over 90 member-states on WPS. CSG reps are periodically invited to speak on issues of concern or that they want raised or discussed at the meeting. NGOWG informs this process, helps with setting agenda, and provides clear cut guidance for discussions. Decisions from this group are taken forward to the UNSC. Member states also approach the heads of CSGs to get ideas and inputs for their respective national statements.

Other WPS advocacy space is following two UNSG reports on WPS. One is the UNSG's report on WPS released in October, a week or two ahead of the Open Debate and UNSG's report on conflict-related sexual violence. The draft of these reports is prepared by UN Women with information they receive from their field offices, from CSGs in conflict countries on the status of implementation of WPS resolutions or on sexual violence in conflict countries. The UNSG also seeks contributions from member-states on this

report. The CSGs in conflict countries have advocacy opportunities to send their shadow reports on the status of implementation of WPS resolutions to UN Women for inclusion in the draft.

UN Women has a steering committee that includes national and international CSG on WPS. The draft is sent to the coalition members for their inputs and comments. This provides an opportunity for coalition CSGs to influence the report and add their objections, suggestions, and improvements to the draft. The CSGs, however, have no ability to further influence the report in the event their suggestions and recommendations are not included in the final report.

Female Civil Society Representation at the Security Council

Resolution 2242 expressed the Council's "intention to invite civil society, including women's organizations, to brief the Council on country-specific considerations and relevant thematic areas". Since this resolution was adopted in 2015, the Council made considerable strides in a more egalitarian representation of civil society and the numbers of civil society female briefers have steadily increased. In 2017, 10 out of the Council's 14 civil society briefers were female; in 2018, the number was 24 out of 30, and in 2019, there were 42 female civil society briefers of the 53.

Briefing the Council members can have repercussions for briefers. In a 2 May 2019 letter to the President of the Security Council, the Permanent Mission of Libya to the UN strongly criticised a briefing given by Inas Miloud, co-founder and director of the Tamazight Women's Movement of Libya, during the annual open debate on conflict-related sexual violence at the Council. In response, the ambassadors of seven Council member states i.e., Belgium, the Dominican Republic, France, Germany, Peru, Poland, and the UK signed a letter to the President of the Security Council expressing belief that despite disagreement of the Libyan Government with the content of Ms. Miloud's briefing, that she will be allowed to continue her work unhindered. (Peacewomen, n.d.)

Similarly, the UNSG in his 2019 annual report on women, peace and security, signalled his extreme concern over harassment of briefers. In his September 2019 report on "Cooperation with the United Nations, its representatives and mechanisms in the field of human rights", he referred to the case of Radhia Al-Mutawake of the Yemeni Mwatana Organization for Human Rights who briefed the Security Council in 2017. She was reportedly arbitrarily detained, and her passport confiscated, seemingly for her engagement with the UN, when attempting to fly out of Yemen.

Implementation of WPS Resolutions

There has been as much success in implementation of the UNSC WPS agenda

over the past years as there have been challenges. The successes relate to norms about sexual violence, rise in references to women in peace processes, in positions of leadership, and in bilateral aid. The international community has adopted several comprehensive normative frameworks with regard to sexual violence in conflict. The Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court that came into force in 2002 outlines a comprehensive list of crimes against women. Since the 1990s, international courts and tribunals have developed sophisticated jurisprudence with regard to these crimes. The Council's call for appointment of a Special Representative on Sexual Violence in Conflict by the Secretary General to report to the Council is yet another established normative mechanism that emerged from the WPS resolutions. (UN Women Global Study, 2015)

Commissions of inquiry and fact-finding missions set up by the Human Rights Council increasingly have a mandate to investigate sexual and gender-based violence, and a roster of experts exists within the international community to support the investigation of these international crimes. Justice and accountability processes that did not traditionally view communal healing as important to truth seeking, reconciliation, memorialisation and reparations for women victims of violations are now recognised in several national and international processes. The CEDAW adopted General Recommendation 30 to provide member states with guidance on issues of WPS for conflict prevention, conflict and post-conflict reconciliations and emphasises the responsibility of every member state to implement resolution 1325. (UN Women Global Study, 2015)

Between 1990 and 2000, before the Council adopted 1325, only 11 per cent of peace agreements signed included a reference to women. Since the adoption of resolution 1325, 27 per cent of peace agreements have referenced women. Of the six agreements resulting from peace talks or national dialogue processes supported by the UN in 2014, 67 per cent contained references relevant to women, peace and security. The number of senior women leaders within the UN has been on the rise, from special envoys of the Secretary General to the first female commander of a peacekeeping mission. Similarly, bilateral aid on gender equality to fragile States has quadrupled in the last decade from a practically non-existent level. (UN Women Global Study, 2015)

However, obstacles and challenges persist and prevent the full implementation of the WPS agenda. National Action Plans (NAPs) for the implementation of UNSCR 1325 are national-level strategy documents that outline a government's approach and course of action for localising action on the Women, Peace and Security Agenda. These documents outline objectives and activities that countries take, both on a domestic and international level, to

secure the human rights of women and girls in conflict settings; prevent armed conflict and violence, including against women and girls; and ensure the meaningful participation of women in peace and security. 103 UN Member states (53%) have adopted NAPs. NAPs of 35 member states (36%) include a budget for implementation. 31 NAPs (32%) include references to and specific action towards disarmament and 70 NAPs (72%) include a role for CSGs for implementation. (Security Council Report, 2022)

Despite the comprehensive normative framework, there are very few actual prosecutions, particularly at the national level. The participation of women in formal peace processes has risen, but a study of 31 major peace processes between 1992 and 2011 revealed that only nine per cent of negotiators were women and only three per cent of the military in UN missions are women, the majority of these are employed as support staff. The two areas of peacemaking and peacekeeping are among the most challenging for ensuring women's equal and meaningful participation. (Security Council Report, 2022)

The rise of violent extremism in many parts of the world has led to a real threat to the lives of women as well as to a cycle of militarisation. Women are often in an ambivalent position in such situations. On the one hand, they reject the strictures on their conduct by violent extremists, and on the other, they have to protect their families and their communities from polarisation and threat. Some women also become fighters and join extremist groups either against their will or out of real conviction. Despite the rhetoric of supporting WPS, funding to enable implementation of WPS programmes and processes remains low across all areas. Bilateral aid has increased to fragile conflict and post-conflict states with regard to gender issues. However, it still remains only six per cent of the total aid package, of which just about two per cent is allocated for peace and security. (Security Council Report, 2022)

Feminist Critiques of WPS Agenda

Feminists point out that the Council's WPS resolutions are essentially the result of political negotiations in a space characterised by power relations between those occupying the space. The negotiations, the space and the actors involved in it has therefore generated a specific understanding of gender and security. (Baumgartner and Jones 1993) Among the main critique of WPS agenda is that the resolutions "does not confront structural roots of gender inequalities including entrenched understandings of patriarchy, masculinity and militarized power (Barnes 2011) are not the root causes of conflict explored in the resolutions." (Porter 2007) The concept of peacebuilding in the resolutions is "too narrow and maintains that peace must be linked to security and justice, freedom from poverty, exclusion and oppression." (Porter 2007)

In the feminist understanding, women are vulnerable because of gender power relations and how it plays out in society. For feminists, therefore, women's vulnerability does not arise from war or is even a specific feature of war, but is rather continuous and persistent. (Santos, Moura & Roque, 2010) Violence in war zones and peace zones are connected in terms of the existence of a parallel "form of war" against women occurring at all times, regardless of whether a context is defined as war or peace. (Eisenstein, 2007, p.12). In the WPS resolutions, however, the problem is defined as one of situations of conflict in which women find themselves, and sexual difference is merely something that women embody. (Jansson & Eduards, 2016)

Essentialises Women

WPS resolutions is built on the essentialist idea that women are more peaceful than men, have much-needed competence to be in peacekeeping missions as mediators in terms of understanding sexual violence or that local women feel safe to report sexual violence to other women, or that the presence of women in peacekeeping missions "may encourage women from local communities to report acts of sexual violence." (UNSC Res. 2009) Therefore, the representation that is stated in 1325 implies that women are representing other "women." Even where women participate in armed forces and participate in war, their job remains to represent women: the "presence of women peacekeepers may encourage local women to participate in the national armed and security forces." (UNSC Res. 2010) Having cast the problem in the above terms, the WPS agenda responds to women's vulnerability in two ways – encouraging/ensuring the participation and enhancing representation of women.

Women as homogenous groups

At the core of the idea of women as representatives is the presumption that women have common interests and are thereby a homogenous group. Within this homogenous group there is a division between women as "representatives" and the women who are "represented". Representatives are ascribed agency, whereas the represented are lacking in it and therefore victims. (Jansson & Eduards, 2016)

To become representatives or protectors, empowered women must be appointed by the men in the country where they are citizens, or by the male dominated institution of the UN. Protected women are thus employed to protect other vulnerable women. In 'the "chain of protection", women participate as protectors while they are simultaneously protected themselves.' (Jansson & Eduards, 2016, p.7)

WPS resolutions imply that gender power dissolves with women protecting other women. The hierarchical power between the "representatives" and the

“represented” is negated on the basis that both parties are of the same sex. It denies differences among women and treats relations among women as non-hierarchical. The problem of skewed power equations in male–female relations is sought to be resolved by clearing men from the peacekeeping space and populating it with women to deal with issues of other women at site of conflict. Though this proposal is motivated to ensure the comfort and respect the needs of the protected women, it also at the same time shields male peacekeepers from any charges of perpetuating gender inequality. (Jansson & Eduards, 2016)

Clearing of men from sexual violence space, however, is not possible because sexual violence invokes legal measures that implies personal responsibility. Rape and sexual violence do not happen without a perpetrator who is often a male. The construction of rape and sexual violence as crimes thus potentially allows for a discussion of how gender relations, violence and power are connected. Such a discussion is, however, not the premise of the WPS agenda. Instead, the logic for discussing sexual violence in the WPS agenda of the UNSC is restricted to the argument that such violence threatens peace and stability. Violence against women impedes peace because it adversely impacts women’s ability to perform their role as agents of peace. To ensure the safety of women as a peacebuilding resource, it is important to protect them from the horrors of war. (Jansson & Eduards, 2016)

Rape and SV part of a violence continuum

Feminist conflict and security studies shows sexual violence is a constant threat to women on a daily basis whether or not the context is of peace or war. (Eisenstein, 2007; MacKinnon, 2007) The WPS resolutions argue that it is the context that defines rape and sexual violence as acute. Therefore, sexual violence and rape in this specific sense are seen as different from both peacetime sexual violence, and the “ordinary” violence of war. Consequently, wartime rape and sexual violence are regarded as a specific and illegitimate form of violence that must be abolished, whereas the peacetime ones are defined as legitimate that can persist or require no specific mention or measures to combat. (Jansson & Eduards, 2016) WPS agenda, therefore, does not regard rape and sexual violence as part of a continuum that exists before the conflict, continues in different and severe forms during conflict and is often normalised in the post-conflict phase.

Conclusion

The feminist critiques of the UNSC WPS agenda are a valid and necessary part of understanding the limitations of WPS. Inclusion of these critiques enable a moving goalpost that can be pursued and achieved incrementally. In the 1990s it was unthinkable that WPS agenda would ever become part of

UNSC. 1325 broke that barrier and there have been incremental advances in WPS agenda with subsequent resolutions enhancing protection, ensuring participation, enabling representation, and making provision for relief and reconciliation. Similar incremental advances could be aimed at by civil society and women's organisations to address root causes of conflict, the structural and geo-political issues that sustain conflicts, acknowledge conflict-related violence as continuing from non-conflict-related violence and treat it as such. In short, the valid critiques do not negate the relevance or importance of the existing WPS agenda. It simply remains an incomplete one that requires additional, simultaneous, and creative advocacy to address the shortcomings and gaps.

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